

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

Stas Gorelik (2026): Review of the ICEWS iDATA (published on Dataverse Project), v. 1.1, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/2C82BF6C-AD7E-4D18-B476-5858EA974052>

Abstract

The ICEWS iDATA collection is part of the Integrated Crisis Early Warning System (ICEWS) project. It provides large-scale, machine-coded event data capturing interactions between socio-political actors worldwide and covering the period from mid-1990s until about 2020. In substantive terms, the dataset covers socio-political interactions: cooperation and conflict between governments, opposition actors, civil society groups, and other organized entities. Events are drawn from English-language reporting as well as from Spanish, Portuguese, and French sources, including both internationally renowned and national media outlets (see also Metadata). The data, codebook and documentation files, explaining the data collection process, are available for download via the link above (no registration required).

Licensed as Attribution and Share Alike: Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL) ("share-alike")

Review of the ICEWS iDATA

by Stas Gorelik

The ICEWS iDATA collection is part of the Integrated Crisis Early Warning System (ICEWS) project (see <https://www.lockheedmartin.com/en-us/capabilities/research-labs/advanced-technology-labs/icews.html>). It provides large-scale, machine-coded event data capturing interactions between socio-political actors worldwide. Events are automatically extracted from news reporting using the BBN ACCENT event coder and follow the CAMEO (Conflict and Mediation Event Observations) taxonomy.

Each observation records a directed interaction (source → target), the type of action, and associated temporal and geographic metadata. The available event-level releases cover the period from 1995 through approximately 2023 in current public distributions. The unit of analysis is a single coded event derived from a sentence in a news article. Events are defined as consisting of a source actor, an event type, and a target actor. Actor attributes include names, sectoral affiliations, and associated countries.

In substantive terms, ICEWS iDATA is geared toward socio-political interactions: cooperation and conflict between governments, opposition actors, civil society groups, and other organized entities. Events are drawn from English-language reporting as well as Spanish, Portuguese, and French sources.

The dataset's main strengths are scale, temporal depth, and standardization. At the same time, several limitations warrant caution. First, as with all media-based event data, coverage is shaped by newsworthiness and media attention rather than the true underlying distribution of political interactions; smaller-scale, routine, or covert actions are likely underreported. Second, event extraction is restricted to sentences 1–6 of each news article, which means that interactions described later in longer reports are systematically missed.

Finally, because the underlying media sources do not include Russian or other widely used languages in the post-Soviet region, politically relevant events in these contexts are more likely to be undercounted or captured only indirectly via international reporting. As a result, ICEWS iDATA is a relatively blunt instrument for studying fine-grained political dynamics in the post-Soviet region and should be used there with particular caution.

Data access: <https://dataverse.harvard.edu/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.7910/DVN/28075>.

Related publications:

- Jäger, K. (2018). "The limits of studying networks via event data: Evidence from the ICEWS dataset." *Journal of Global Security Studies*, 3(4), 498–511.
- Shilliday, A. & Lautenschlager, J. (2012). "Data for a worldwide ICEWS and ongoing research." In *Advances in Design for Cross-Cultural Activities Part I*. CRC Press.

- Ward, M., Metternich, N., Carrington, C., Dorff, C., Gallop, M., Hollenbach, F., Schultz, A. & Weschle, S. (2012). "Geographical models of crises: Evidence from ICEWS." In *Advances in Design for Cross-Cultural Activities Part I*. CRC Press.